

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

A VISION FOR RURAL AREAS

MAP Position Paper

LONG-TERM VISION FOR RURAL AREAS: CONTRIBUTION FROM 20 SCIENCE- SOCIETY-POLICY PLATFORMS

MAP POSITION PAPER

CIRCULAR BIO-ECONOMY

LITHUANIA

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Contact information

Facilitator | dr. Zivile Gedminaite-Raudone, zivile.gedminaite@laei.lt

Monitor | dr. Rita Vilke, rita.vilke@laei.lt

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1. Introduction

Inhabitants of rural regions, activities and the whole rural areas have faced considerable changes in recent decades in Lithuania as in the whole Europe due to several key factors as economic and demographical changes, technological development, socio-economic changes and policy developments at national and at the EU level. The question is what future we can foresee for rural areas both in Lithuania and Europe. There are many initiatives to organise various projects, research work and high-level discussions on rural areas in Europe. This Position paper also gives an input to the discussions on the future of rural areas.

Position paper is aimed to introduce challenges, opportunities and long-term vision until 2040 of rural areas of Lithuania identified by the MAP of Lithuania in 2020. Position paper was prepared using a 6-step Delphi method, combining research, use of quantitative data with expert interviews and surveys. The following 6 steps were applied: (1) Desk research and context analysis (March-May 2020); (2) Interviews using 2 Focus group meetings (May 2020); (3) Interview analysis, writing MAP Discussion paper and preparation of survey (May-June 2020); (4) MAP survey (July-August 2020); (5) Survey analysis (September 2020); (6) Validation of results (October 2020).

The Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) of Lithuania is “Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania” (CBioLit). This platform is coordinated by the Lithuanian Institute of Agrarian Economics. MAP of the SHERPA project is defined as “the forum for two-way exchanges of ideas for co-learning and co-creation of knowledge with actors at

European and regional levels”. Lithuanian MAP covers whole territory of Lithuania. “Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania” (CBioLit) is a newly established platform. Quadruple helix approach was used to identify active members of the MAP of Lithuania: science (universities and research institutes); society: private sector and civil society organisations (NGOs); policy (public sector).

2. Headline message

Rural areas of Lithuania up to 2040 – rural regions with modern villages in a partnership as an attractive place to live. Smart villages with selected strategy for development where live, work and invest communities of farmers, craftsmen’s, other businesses applying principles of cooperation using renewable resources to produce local products and sell it to consumers. Such principles ensure protection of biodiversity and creation/preserving of rich landscape.

Keywords: rural areas, sustainability, local food, rural communities.

3. Key scientific evidence

Key scientific evidence on the key development trends of Lithuanian rural areas has been collected during the SHERPA Desk research (for detailed information see the Discussion Paper “Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania” (CBioLit). Lithuania-specific rural development perspectives are focused on most sensitive changes, undergone by Lithuanian rural areas, namely:

1. demographic shift,
2. climate change and environmental services,
3. change in production and diversification of rural economy,
4. infrastructure and basic services,
5. digitalisation and smart ruralities,
6. inequalities and well-being in rural areas.

Demographic shift. The decrease in the Lithuanian rural population is the most striking feature, assessing the situation in rural regions of Lithuania. The declining rural population has a direct impact on population density in rural areas. The main factors of population decline are the negative rate of natural population growth and the constant net emigration. As a result of these demographic changes, the structure of the country's population is scarcely changing: the population is aging; the number of young and working-age population is decreasing.

Climate change and environmental services. Lithuania has made a number of international commitments to contribute to climate change mitigation goals. The impact of livestock farming on climate change has decreased; GHG emissions from the crop subsector remain increasing in total GHG emissions from agricultural activities. Extreme meteorological phenomena increased farm losses, reduced production stability, interest in farming and willingness to contribute to the development and modernisation of the sector to fight climate change. According to the production of renewable energy per ha of used land, Lithuania lags far behind the EU average. Energy efficiency of agriculture and forestry keep increasing in Lithuania.

Change in production and diversification of rural economy. The agricultural production sector in Lithuania is dominated by small producers; the sector is fragmented; the food processing industry and retail trade are highly concentrated. The level of cooperation between farmers remains low. Involvement of farmers in market-oriented production models start changing. In Lithuania, there have been significant increase in initiatives to develop the local food system and short food supply chains using various direct sales methods for agricultural and food products. Community-initiated local development is gaining increasingly important role in rural economy. Volunteering, community initiatives and partnerships, which are actively developed in rural areas of the country, still hold unused potential to diversify the rural economy and alongside solve the problems of employment and social inclusion of the rural population in Lithuania.

Infrastructure and basic services. The general state of Lithuanian infrastructure has been improved after entering the EU. The main problem in organising the process of service provision in rural areas of Lithuania arose due to the decreased population density - the number of service users also decreased. This led to the rising cost of public services; services provision concentrates in several regional institutions. Rural population's access to public transport, education, health and social services scarcely become limited; this in turn leads to social exclusion and other deepening social problems in Lithuanian rural areas.

Digitalisation and smart ruralities. The key trends related to the rise of digitalisation and smart ruralities in Lithuania are foreseen from the two basic perspectives: first, overall digitalisation of rural areas in terms of access to the internet on a daily basis including the use of e-services, and second, digitalisation of agriculture. Internet access and e-public services are in favourable conditions (broadband coverage in Lithuanian rural areas reached 98%). In Lithuanian agriculture the application of advanced technologies and digitalisation is not yet widespread; it is necessary to encourage the country's farmers to use the opportunities provided by these innovations.

Inequalities and well-being in rural areas. Negative demographic processes threaten the continuation of Lithuanian farming traditions, the creation of public values in the future and, at the same time, the viability of rural areas. Unemployment remains a huge problem in Lithuanian rural areas: insufficient professional training, lack of qualifications and entrepreneurship. Low income of the rural population and social exclusion arise from long-term payment of social benefits, lack of social integration and active measures to fight unemployment; no motivation and will to seek prosperity.

4. Summary of the outcomes of the Delphi

This section provides the outcomes of an applied the Delphi method to prepare a long-term vision for rural areas of Lithuania until 2040. Position paper covers the results from the interviews, from the survey and from the consensus meeting. Position paper was prepared using a 6-step Delphi method, combining research, use of quantitative data with expert interviews and surveys. The following 6 steps were applied: (1) desk research and context analysis (March-May 2020); (2) interviews using 2 Focus group meetings (May 2020);

(3) interview analysis, writing MAP Discussion paper and preparation of survey (May-June 2020); (4) MAP survey (July-August 2020); (5) survey analysis (September 2020); (6) validation of results (October 2020).

4.1. Challenges and opportunities in the next 20 years

Rural areas in Lithuania cover significant amount of territory in Lithuania with different geographical, economic, societal, environmental and cultural background. Inhabitants of rural regions, activities and the whole rural areas have faced considerable changes in recent decades in Lithuania as in the whole Europe due to several key factors as economic and demographical changes, technological development, socioeconomic changes and policy developments at national and the EU level. Identification of challenges and opportunities of rural areas in Lithuania are necessary for creation of future development plans for these places.

The following challenges for rural areas in Lithuania were identified at the expert group discussion:

1. *Demographic shift:* depopulation and ageing. Rural areas in Lithuania are facing depopulation because of internal migration of young residents to cities and external migration to work abroad. Remaining rural residents are getting older and rural areas are becoming depopulated with elderly people.
2. *Infrastructure and basic services.* Main problems are related with (1) low density of inhabitants in rural areas; (2) costs for infrastructure maintenance; (3) availability of services in rural area: location of kindergartens, primary schools and secondary schools; post services; hospitals, supermarkets; (4) quality of services related with education (primary schools and secondary schools); (5) difficulties of elderly to get to necessary services located outside of living place; (6) not sufficient skills of elderly to use possibilities of digitalisation; (7) problem of old unused buildings and houses in rural areas – they interrupt landscape of rural areas and attractiveness to live in a village.
3. *Diversification of rural economy.* Rural areas are still observed as working place in farms or enterprises related with farming activities. Key challenge is to diversify rural economy with different economic activities in services, industry, and construction as there are increasing possibilities to work remotely because of digitalisation possibilities in Lithuania. Diversification of activities of small farms or/and other initiatives providing other services. In some cases, for successful development of rural areas are opposition/no networking between rural communities and farmers.
4. *Competencies of inhabitants* of rural areas and public institutions responsible for implementation of rural policy in Lithuania. (1) Elderly inhabitants face problems using possibilities proposed by digitalised services. (2) Farmers and members of rural communities lack knowledge leading to innovation. (3) Employees of public institution are not able to reflect to current needs of various actors of rural areas. Low motivation to update their knowledge.
5. *Low intentions* of rural inhabitants *for integration, cooperation, co-creation.*
6. *Lack of motivation, lack of self-confidence. Lack of confidence between different generations.* On one hand, initiatives for young people are supported; on the other hand, elderly do not trust young people (including also farming activities, decision-making process).
7. Decision making process for rural regions in Lithuania. *Weak strategic planning for rural regions.* Gaps between institutions – decision-makers at national level, municipalities, local representatives, local communities and other rural actors.

Survey results on above identified challenges for rural areas in Lithuania on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important) are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Main challenges of Lithuanian rural areas.

Survey results have demonstrated that the most important challenges for rural areas in Lithuania are demographic shift (91,7 % stated as 'Very important' or 'Fairly important'), competencies of inhabitants in rural areas (100 % stated as 'Very important' or 'Fairly important'), infrastructure and basic services, also diversification of rural economy (in both options 83,3 % stated as 'Very important' or 'Fairly important').

The following opportunities for rural areas in Lithuania were identified at the expert group discussion:

1. *Potential of digitalisation.* Large network of high-speed broadband services. Digitalisation of activities, access to online services, reducing connectivity gap between remote rural areas and cities.
2. *Human resources.* Highly motivated, hardworking people. Modern programmes at universities reflecting current needs of rural areas including farming.
3. *Strong urban-rural relations.* City residents have strong relation with rural areas as previous residents of rural areas (themselves, or their parents used to live there). Purpose of visit to rural areas is related with spending leisure time in nature (various types of tourism: slow, transformative, ecological, and others), visiting families or friends in rural areas, other activities.
4. *Covid-19 pandemic situation* have opened a need to search for a place outside cities with more space for living, spending time in nature. Rural areas a perfect place for remote work for employees of different professions using high speed broadband.
5. Local food: potential to strengthen *local food market*; short supply chain of local food; *tourism development.* Encourage consumption of Lithuanian production.
6. *Opportunities by Green deal* initiated by the EU. Strategies for development of rural areas in Lithuania should reflect on ecological farming and other ecological initiatives, less pollution, environmental requirements.

Survey results on above identified opportunities for rural areas in Lithuania in the next 20 years up to 2040 on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important) are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Main opportunities for Lithuanian rural areas in the next 20 years up to 2040

Survey results have demonstrated that the most important opportunities in the next 20 years for rural areas in Lithuania are opportunities proposed by Green Deal (100 % stated as 'Fairly important' or 'Very important'), local food and tourism development (91,7 % stated as 'Fairly important' or 'Very important'), and human resources (91,7 % stated as 'Fairly important' or 'Very important').

4.2. Desirable future for 2040

Discussion on desirable future for rural areas is a long-lasting process in Lithuania and it will continue in the coming years as large territory of Lithuania is rural areas and cities cover only small part of it. 1/3 of population lives in rural areas of Lithuania. Another part of population that lives in the cities have close relation with rural areas as their parents or grandparents used to live in rural areas or still live there. Many of residents from cities and rural areas still have good skills for growing vegetables, fruits and spending time in the countryside.

Rural areas in Lithuania is still in the favour for farmers particularly large farms as they play important part in rural economy and have good tools in lobbying for decision making process with public authorities in Lithuania responsible for implementation of agricultural policy in Lithuania. Small and medium farms and entities also try to find their role but their power to influence is not as high or important as other actors. Rural communities are becoming more active last decades and in Lithuania there are a number of perfect examples of successful development of places where communities are known with interesting projects, more intensive involvement of local residents and even attracting new people to live in these places. Also new initiatives are becoming more popular in rural areas of Lithuania as slow, educational or transformative tourism, new business models established from residents from cities who decided to move from cities to villages (various culture-uncommon thematic villages, local food restaurants, therapy centres, etc.) or various networking initiatives between urban and rural areas (as rent a piece of garden project, food basket to your home, etc.). Good practice examples can inspire many potential newcomers to the rural areas of Lithuania who are still searching for activities where they can realise themselves.

Another trend with rural areas in Lithuania is related with moving to suburban areas close to large cities aiming to be close to nature, have more living space and with good distance to all necessary infrastructure.

Epidemic situation with Covid-19 even opened more discussion with increased potential for rural areas. Rural areas are seen as attractive and safe place to live especially for those who can work remotely as high-quality Internet broadband is covered in all territory of Lithuania. Also, this situation opened more opportunities to

focus on internal food market and to strengthen short supply chains of local food; also, by exploiting more tools to create networks between rural areas and cities for consumption of local food.

In the light of the above-mentioned circumstances, desirable future of rural areas by the experts was highlighted in the following features:

1. Rural areas are place for residents of various professions as rurality is not equal to farming by finding various roles for economic activities by working in place or remotely. Residents or newcomers can focus on new innovative initiatives using unique natural or cultural resources of this place (slow, transformative tourism, etc.) or create new non-agricultural business (small or medium food processing entities, wood construction, etc.).
2. Creation of desirable infrastructure in the region and locally. Public authorities should assess rules for creation or maintenance of needed infrastructure in the region: by defining how much time is needed to get to the hospital, post, supermarket, school, kindergarten, etc. Infrastructure in villages also should be attractive by finding tools how to solve problems of non-used old living houses or previous farm buildings for many years as this neighbourhood do not attract newcomers to choose their place as new home.
3. Specialisation of the regions. Inhabitants of rural regions in Lithuania should choose specialisation of the territory to use resources in the best way: regions with focus on agriculture, regions with unique natural resources for development of various forms of tourism, regions with focus on non-agricultural activities, e.g., social business, cooperatives with focus on processing of agricultural products, wood processing companies, etc.).
4. Implementation of RIS3 strategy. Priority on supporting biologically valuable food. Biologically valuable food for consumers. Food grown with ecological, clean technologies. Biologically valuable for people, the environment and nature.
5. Local food: potential to strengthen local food market; short supply chain of local food; tourism development. Encourage consumption of Lithuanian production. Increase education skills on benefits of local food for consumers. Decrease transportation of imported products; focus on consumption of local food.
6. Education in universities and colleges. Need for innovation brokers and mentors. Need for distance learning to get new skills and increase knowledge in some interested areas. Need for continuous professional development.

Survey results on desirable future of rural areas on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important) are provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Desirable future of rural areas in Lithuania

Survey results have demonstrated that all 6 areas for desirable future of rural areas in Lithuania proposed in by the experts in the Focus group meetings, were highly ranked also in the survey with equal or higher than 83 % stated as 'Fairly important' or 'Very important'.

A vision for rural areas of Lithuania up to 2040 – rural regions with modern villages in a partnership as an attractive place to live. 91,3 % of survey respondents supported this statement. Smart villages with selected strategy for development where live, work and invest communities of farmers, craftsmen's, other businesses applying principles of cooperation using renewable resources to produce local products and sell it to consumers. Such principles ensure protection of biodiversity and creation/preserving of rich landscape. Rural regions are administrative-territorial regions and not a number of individual settlements with effective and efficient planning tools for provisions of needed services and infrastructure based on the principle of networking: transport (roads), education (kindergartens, schools), social and other services (hospitals, primary care centres, day care centres, etc.).

4.3. Enablers to achieve the vision

The following challenges were identified in reaching the vision for future of rural areas in Lithuania up to 2040:

1. Lack of long-term planning process for rural areas in Lithuania based on results of elections. Not only when focusing on vision for rural areas but also for other sectors too. RIS3 strategy is too broad.
2. Unequal power of rural actors to influence decision-making process in Lithuania. Urban residents are not intensively involved in decision-making process for strategic planning for future of rural areas in Lithuania. Only vision where all actors can find their role in rural areas can be alive and successfully implemented.
3. Lack of education skills and knowledge on various topics for all triple helix members: policy, society and NGO. Policy: focus on new initiatives and practices to create prosperous of rural areas based

on successful initiatives locally and internationally. Society: best practice examples; coaching, mentoring. Science: new programmes; new ways of involvement of students and elderly in long-life learning reflecting current tendencies.

Enablers to achieve the vision of rural areas of Lithuania up to 2040 are provided in Table 4.

Table 4. Enablers to achieve the vision for rural areas of Lithuania.

6 enablers were identified as very helpful to achieve the vision of rural areas of Lithuania up to 2040 with equal or higher than 83 % stated as 'Very helpful'.

Annex 1. Methodology used in the MAP

Position paper was prepared using a 6-step Delphi method, combining research, use of quantitative data with expert interviews and surveys.

The following 6 steps were applied for this paper:

Step 1. Desk research and context analysis. Analysis was performed on March-May 2020.

Step 2. Interviews using 2 focus group meetings. Both Focus meetings were organised in May 2020. 1st meeting (21 May 2020) was on-line meeting. 10 MAP members – experts attended this meeting. 2nd meeting (26 May 2020) was physical meeting. 7 MAP members – experts attended this meeting.

Programme of the Focus group meeting is provided below.

Table 5. Programme of the Focus group meeting

9:50 –10:00	Registration
10:00 – 10:10	Introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dr. Zivile Gedminaite-Raudone, Head of Rural development department, Facilitator of SHERPA MAP in Lithuania • dr. Rita Vilke, Senior researcher of Rural development department, Monitor of SHERPA MAP in Lithuania
10:10 – 10:40	Discussion (1st question): Opportunities and challenges in the next 20 years: what do you see as the main opportunities and challenges coming up until 2040?
10:40 – 11:10	Discussion (2nd question): What is your vision for your rural territory by 2040?
11:10 –11:50	Discussion (3rd question): What are challenges in reaching the visions?
11:50 – 12:00	Conclusions and insights

Step 3. Interview analysis, writing MAP Discussion paper and preparation of survey. All tasks from Step 3 were performed on May-June 2020.

Step 4. MAP survey took place on July-August 2020. Experts completed survey using Survey Monkey tool (Link: <http://www.apklausa.lt>).

Survey questionnaire for Lithuanian case is provided below.

Step 5. Survey analysis was completed in September 2020. 12 respondents out of 15 responded to this survey (80 percent). Respondents of this survey were experts of the MAP “Circular Bio-economy – Lithuania (CBioLit)” of Lithuania.

Figure 1. Background of survey experts

Background of survey experts

Step 6. Validation of results was organised on 28 October 2020 in Consensus meeting organised online using MS Teams programme. The number of participants in the consensus meeting: xx participants.

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear respondent,

The Sherpa project (rural-interfaces.eu) cordially invites you to participate in a survey to identify key challenges and opportunities, enablers and hinders in rural Lithuania up until 2040.

The survey contains 8 mostly 'quick click' multiple choice questions. The estimated time for completion is 10 minutes.

Your responses are anonymous and confidential. They will be analysed and presented to a Lithuanian expert group – the so-called Multi-Actor Platform. The results will also be shared with the European Commission and as a contribution to its Long-term vision for rural areas.

Your feedback is important, and we greatly appreciate you taking the time to complete this survey.

Thank you!

From the options below, which one describes your background best? Please choose only one option

- Public Sector / National Level
- Public Sector / Local Level
- NGO / Civil Society
- Business

- Research
- Private person

A group of experts and different societal actors from the Lithuanian Multi-Actor Platform discussed a number of themes and topics they consider being relevant for rural areas. The next questions allow you to state how important you perceive the topics to be and also rank them.

On a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important) how important are the themes and topics mentioned below for you?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Important	Fairly important	Very important
<i>Demographic shift: depopulation and ageing</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Infrastructure and basic services</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Diversification of rural economy</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Competencies of inhabitants</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Low intentions of rural inhabitants for integration, cooperation, cocreation</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Lack of motivation, lack of self-confidence. Lack of confidence between different generations.</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Weak strategic planning for rural regions</i>	0	0	0	0	0

Rural areas are well prepared for and resilient to acute shocks, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with this statement.

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	0	0	0	0

Rural areas are well prepared for and resilient to long term challenges, such as demographic change.

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with this statement.

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Opportunities in the next 20 years.

How important are the opportunities below?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Important	Fairly important	Very important
<i>Potential of digitalization.</i> Large network of high-speed broadband services. Digitalization of activities, access to online services, reducing connectivity gap between remote rural areas and cities.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Human resources.</i> Highly motivated, hardworking people. Modern programmes at universities reflecting current needs of rural areas including farming.	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Strong urban-rural relations.</i> City residents have strong relation with rural areas as previous residents of rural areas (themselves, or their parents used to live there). Purpose of visit to rural areas is related with spending leisure time in nature (various types of tourism: slow, transformative, ecological, and so on), visiting families or friends in rural areas, other activities.	<input type="radio"/>				

<p><i>Covid-19 pandemic situation</i> have opened a need to search for a place outside cities with more space for living, spending time in nature. Rural areas a perfect place for remote work for employees of different professions using high speed broadband.</p>	<input type="radio"/>				
<p><i>Local food and tourism development.</i> Potential to strengthen local food market; short supply chain of local food; tourism development. Supply of biologically valuable food is not sufficient. Encourage consumption of Lithuanian production.</p>	<input type="radio"/>				
<p><i>Opportunities by Green Deal</i> initiated by the EU. Strategies for development of rural areas in Lithuania should reflect on ecological farming and other ecological initiatives, less pollution, environmental requirements.</p>	<input type="radio"/>				

5. Rural Vision Lithuania 2040

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the statements below.

In 2040, Lithuanian rural areas...

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
...for all professions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

<p>Rural areas will become a place for residents of various professions: rurality - is not only for farming anymore! New roles and economic activities by working in place or remotely. Focus on new innovative initiatives using unique natural or cultural resources of the place (slow, transformative tourism, etc.), creation of new non-agricultural business (small or medium food processing entities, wood construction, etc.).</p>					
<p><i>...with desirable infrastructure.</i> Creation of desirable infrastructure in regionally and locally by newly established rules, based on regional demands: how much time is needed to get to the hospital, post, supermarket, school, kindergarten? Tools for solving problems of non-used old living houses, previous farm buildings to attract newcomers to choose these as a place for new home.</p>	o	o	o	o	o
<p><i>...with regional specialization.</i> Inhabitants of rural regions in Lithuania should choose their specializations to use their resources in the best way: regions with focus on agriculture, regions with unique natural resources for development of various tourism forms, regions with focus on non-agricultural activities (e.g., social business, cooperatives with focus on agricultural products processing, wood processing companies, etc.).</p>	o	o	o	o	o
<p><i>...with implemented smart specialization strategy.</i> Priority on supporting biologically valuable food. Biologically valuable food for consumers. Food grown with ecological, clean technologies. Biologically valuable for people, the environment and nature. Fewer emissions as results of producing biologically sustainable products.</p>	o	o	o	o	o
<p><i>...with developed local food networks.</i> Strengthened local food market; short supply chain of local food; tourism development. Encouraged consumption of Lithuanian products. Increased education and skills on benefits of local food for consumers. Decrease</p>	o	o	o	o	o

transportation of imported products; focus on consumption of local food. Orientation to the local market: direct contacts with consumers, reduced risk of open market, obtained higher price, decreased proportion in the number of intermediaries.					
... with gap-focused education and continuous improvement. Education in universities and colleges. Need for innovation brokers and mentors. Need for distance learning to get new skills and increase knowledge in particular interested areas. Need for continuous professional development.	○	○	○	○	○

Rural Vision Lithuania 2040 - short statement

Discussions in expert groups and different societal actors from the Lithuanian Multi-Actor Platform accelerated to formulate the Rural Vision 2040 for Lithuania as following:

“A vision for rural areas of Lithuania up to 2040 – rural regions with modern villages in partnership as an attractive place to live.”

Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the formulated vision.

- Agree
- Disagree:

In case You disagree with proposed Rural Vision 2040 for Lithuania, please suggest alternative formulation:

Fighting challenges in reaching the vision

Please indicate to what extent the proposed opportunities would be helpful for implementing the Rural Vision Lithuania 2040

	Not helpful at all	Neither helpful nor hindering	Very helpful
National policy framework (enabling place-based strategies)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interconnectedness between policies on national and local level	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Availability of local knowledge and small-scale data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Existing partnerships and cooperation between different policy levels	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Existing networks of local actors	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Existing networks between rural and urban actors	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Trust between authorities and society	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6. Anything else?

Do you have any comments?

Rural development up until 2040 - Challenges, opportunities, enablers and hinders

THANK YOU!

